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MOTIVATIONAL SEMINARS AND TRAINING AS AN INSTRUMENT FOR PERSONAL STIMULATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN HOSPITALITY BUSINESS

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Abstract

This article reveals the importance of training and professionalism of staff in a hotel. The authors develop a mechanism for training and stages of adaptation of hotel employees as a tool for motivating staff. Seminars and trainings divided into several areas, systematized into courses that clearly formulate the actions of employees in the development strategy of the hotel itself. This training gives employees confidence, where after each training they clearly begin to understand the activities and goals of the organization, thereby motivating them to achieve the strategic goals of the organization.

Keywords: *personnel, personnel training, trainings, seminars, hotel, tourism, personnel motivation, personal stimulation, human capital, hospitality business.*

1. Introduction. Relevance of the research topic.

Against the backdrop of today's economic instability in many countries, the role of tourism remains relevant, and is also one of the most developing sectors of the world economy. The hospitality sector is an important social, economic and cultural category, one of the fundamental components of the tourism industry, which is adequate in development to the main stages of the evolution of human society.

2. "Personal decides everything".

The main slogan for the development of the hotel and tourism business, "Personnel decides everything", is an integral part of the quality production of services, providing not only services, but also customer satisfaction in this industry. Therefore, the hotel industry, as an important infrastructure of the tourism sector, determines the development of the tourism sector.

Modern and developed hotels are increasingly focusing their efforts on the training and professionalism of hotel staff, where the main focus is on motivational seminars that simultaneously develop the professionalism of hotel staff [10, P.573-577].

Motivational seminars and staff training for most hotels is now of particular importance. This is due to the fact that working in a market environment places high demands on the level of staff qualifications, knowledge and skills of employees. And, quite quickly. It is only necessary to systematically apply this "tool" in the team. A side effect of these activities is that it improves the personal lives of employees along the way.

3. Experience of leading specialists of the hotel industry in personnel training.

Each hotel has its own distinctive feature, which is a prerequisite that satisfies the largest number of customers. For example: At the heart of Merriott's work

with personnel is the rule adopted by the founder of this empire: "Take care of your employees, and they will take care of your customers." It is the employees that the organization considers its main capital.

According to N. A. Zaitseva, "motivation" is an internal process of a person's conscious choice of one or another type of behavior, determined by the complex influence of external (stimuli) and internal (motives) factors. The management of the administration of a hotel enterprise should include staff incentive systems that are aimed at the effective management of employees, their labor and personal improvement, training and encouragement [12].

4. Development and systematization of the training program and professional adaptation of hotel staff.

Along with motivational programs, the company provides its staff with the opportunity to learn and improve at the workplace, and new vacancies in hotels are filled in priority from among the employees.

As Kurbanov A.J. notes. "The quality and efficiency of knowledge, of course, as an important capital of the economy and opportunities for growth and development matter. The degree of its effect depends on the correct use of the shaping process. In the learning process, one or more groups of abilities that are directly related to the learning process develop. A continuous learning process increases the quality of human capital, thereby ensuring the development of economic spheres" [5; P. 141-148, 4; P. 65-76].

Based on this, we can say that staff training is the most important means of achieving the company's strategic goal - to improve the service to its guests. The program of training and professional adaptation of hotel staff can be divided into several areas (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. The mechanism of training and professional adaptation of personnel hotels

5. Research Objectives. Analysis of the training program.

Let's analyze all the points of the training program:

1. Further, employees must be trained using a series of trainings developed by the company related to working with the company's clientele [1,2,3]:

- • training (Brand Standards) tells about the brand standards of the given hotel;
- • training "Responses to comments and complaints of clients" (Guest Response) is devoted to working out the technique of responding to complaints and comments of the client;
- • the program "Commitment to the principles of hospitality" (Loyalty) tells about the specifics and prospects of the hotel business;
- • training on the rules of telephone etiquette;
- • sales training;
- • the program "Behavior in case of fire and other extreme situations" (Fire&Emergency);
- • training "Striving for excellence in service" (Service Excellence) examines various aspects of guest service, rules of conduct in standard and non-standard situations;
- • "Certification" program.

The "Certification" program is one of the unique developments of hotel companies - a program of professional adaptation of new employees in the workplace. In each department, the implementation of this program is carried out by managers together with department trainers. It is based on a detailed training plan

for a beginner, which spells out all the skills and knowledge related mainly to professional activities.

After the plan is drawn up, a brochure is developed, which contains a description of all the rules, standards and procedures of work. Each newcomer is assigned an experienced employee who, day after day, step by step, teaches him everything he needs to know and be able to do. The training period under the "Certification" program lasts three months (trial period for a new employee), so that by the end of it, the employee can perform his functional duties on an equal basis with other employees of the department.

1. Trainings for senior, middle and junior managers.

The next direction is developing trainings for top, middle and junior managers. The purpose of these programs is to develop managerial qualities and skills.

Each manager should have a so-called "profile" - a document that contains information about his education, courses, seminars and trainings. This information helps the HR department in analyzing training needs and selecting exactly those training programs for the manager that are most relevant to them [5,8].

Trainings for managers are conducted in the following areas:

- ✓ programs dedicated to the development of leadership qualities;
- ✓ training programs dedicated to the training of managers in a narrow, specialized area (Operations Trainings). These are programs for managers of the Restaurant Service, the Reception and Accommodation Service, the Hotel Services Service, etc.;

- ✓ training "Time Management";
- ✓ training "Delegation of powers";
- ✓ training "E-mail Etiquette";
- ✓ "Believe in yourself" training, one part of which is devoted to negotiating and resisting attempts at psychological manipulation;
- ✓ At the request of many managers, the training "Effective Interview" was created and implemented (since company managers are involved in the interview process when selecting personnel);
- ✓ advanced training programs for managers in the field of information technology.

A modern hotel is a very complex structure, in which many computer programs of varying degrees of complexity operate. Hotels believe that even a middle manager should be fluent in a computer, therefore, attention is paid to training in this area.

2. Trainings for the training of trainers of departments [11].

This is a program called "Train the Trainer". Naturally, events taking place in the hotel, VIP visits and urgent problems for the department are discussed at these mini-trainings.

4. Trainings for interacting departments. A cross-training program has been created for employees of those departments that interact in the course of work (for example, the Reception and Accommodation Service, Butler Service and Hotel Services, Restaurants and Room Service). This is an employee exchange program between interacting departments, when employees get the opportunity to work in another department for several days, which allows them to better know the specifics of the work of colleagues and reduces the possibility of misunderstandings and inconsistencies in work.

5. Highly specialized trainings. One of the areas of work in the field of personnel training is the so-called "professional" trainings. The company attracts its managers, many of whom are high professionals in their field, to conduct various highly specialized trainings. An example is seminars on the study of the features of training in servicing VIP banquets, etc.

Further, the effectiveness of the trainings is determined and evaluated:

The quality of staff training is characterized by the following indicators:

1. *The main indicator is "The Guest Satisfaction Survey".*

By filling out special questionnaires, guests evaluate the quality of services according to various criteria - from the quality of cleaning and the condition of guest rooms and the hotel as a whole to the level of friendliness and attention from the staff (telephone operators also accept any information from customers and enter it into a common database). According to the report, which is compiled on the basis of these assessments, one can judge the quality of service provided in hotels in comparison with other hotels in the world and how much the situation has changed compared to the previous reporting period. If the indicators for any criterion have decreased, then a set of measures (of which training is an integral part) is developed specifically for this "problem zone".

2. *Annual survey of employees' opinions regarding their satisfaction with the quality of working life in the company.*

One of the items of the questionnaire is the item on satisfaction with the quality of the corporate training system, which is recorded in the summary form "Action plan". At the end of the year, an overall analysis (on all indicators) of the effectiveness of training programs and training needs for each department is carried out. Based on this analysis, the department manager draws up a training plan for hotel employees (together with the training department) for the next year, highlighting priority areas of work. Training allows not only to preserve and disseminate among employees the traditional values and priorities of the organizational culture, but also to promote new approaches and guidelines. Thus, the organization increases the value of the human resources at its disposal. The staff gets the opportunity to accumulate knowledge, skills and abilities and transform them into the experience of successful activities in the interests of the company [9, P. 68-78].

Purpose of the training:

1. Increase employee confidence in their abilities;
2. Remove errors in work;
3. Increase orders and profits;
4. Get information about modern standards of the hospitality industry.
5. Master the process of creating and implementing corporate service standards.
6. Understand the factors of effective work with staff in the hotel, how to achieve a real increase in the level of service.
7. Transfer effective tools for working with employees and improving the quality of customer service
8. Unite the team.

The main secret of a successful business in sales, technology development, and in general - go and do it! But with rare exceptions, people are not robots: you can't "push the button" and keep a constant pace. But it is necessary. So that this "go and do" thing does not fade away, many companies order personal growth trainings, classes to increase sales, seminars to motivate employees. They deal with the employees themselves. That's right ... And here the second secret of development becomes relevant, which many underestimate - the regularity of classes. It is impossible to hold an employee development training at the beginning of the year and then expect consistently high self-motivation and performance from all employees throughout the year. Constant and varied training is a big part of success.

Next, consider four tips for motivating staff for management (advice to managers):

1. Team motivation requires sincere communication. This is a simple human participation in the lives of those who are now partly dependent on you. People will appreciate it. The well-being of an employee in this company depends very well on you.

2. Offer people an honest conversation, "no conclusions" at the end of the conversation, and ask a simple question "Why do you think so much about money?"

3. Think more about the success of your subordinates. Then your success will come automatically (after

all, it is your department that will flourish under your leadership). When we are motivated, it is easy and pleasant for us to work.

4. Most importantly, we must not forget that we all need each other! Success is not possible alone. Even a solitary genius needs a "market" for the application of his talent.

Thus, we note that one of the proven methods for the competitiveness of hotels and tourism in general is the professionalism and literacy of tourism personnel. Continuous professional development, staff training and development are tools that increase work efficiency and profits, and help self-development.

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